

SOIL MOISTURE ESTIMATION FROM POLARIMETRIC SAR USING A PHYSICS AWARE AI MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the synergy of electromagnetic data modeling and Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms for soil moisture retrieval over agricultural fields using Polarimetric SAR (PolSAR) data. SAR acquisitions are considered as a valuable source for accurate estimation of soil moisture in agricultural areas. However, its retrievals are influenced by various factors, including vegetation cover. In this context, the polarimetric information of SAR acquisitions allows the interpretation of the occurring scattering processes. The proposed approach involves a physics-aware AI algorithm based on two Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), trained on electromagnetic (EM) model simulations at L-band. Starting from a full polarimetric Covariance Matrix, the first AI model separates the different scattering contributions, estimating surface and double-bounce scattering mechanisms while minimizing the attenuation effects caused by the vegetation layer. Then, the estimated surface and double-bounce components are fed to an additional AI model to retrieve soil moisture. Field campaign data over actual corn fields were considered and ingested by the EM model to generate synthetic SAOCOM-like case studies which were used to validate the approach within the simulated domain.

Index Terms— Soil moisture estimation, polarimetric SAR (PolSAR), decomposition, physics-aware AI, Explainable AI.

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil moisture is a crucial geophysical parameter for environmental monitoring, especially in the agriculture applications domain. The accuracy of soil moisture maps can be a valuable information, useful for resources management strategies, e.g., irrigation plans, crop selection, or harvest predictions. In this context, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data have been extensively used to

estimate soil moisture over agricultural areas [1-2] due to their inherent sensitivity to the variations in soil conditions. However, soil moisture retrievals derived from SAR are also influenced by factors such as topography, incidence angle, soil roughness, and vegetation cover. These elements significantly impact the received signal due to attenuation and scattering mechanisms occurring on the observed surface. Specifically, the complexity increases when vegetation is present, as the waves travel through the vegetation interacting with its structure and then with the underlying surface, so that the measured scattered signal embeds the effects of both vegetation and soil [3]. To decompose these effects, the polarimetric information of SAR acquisitions can be leveraged, and various polarimetric decompositions have been implemented over the years to address the problem. Bio-geophysical parameters retrievals based on SAR data incorporate more often AI models which, capitalizing on their ability to discern complex patterns and relationships within extensive datasets, can increase the accuracy of the estimation. However, implementing supervised AI algorithms poses a significant challenge due to the need for labeled data. Additionally, the observation domain is incapable of providing ground truth data representing the different scattering components since the measured scattered radar signal is the result of a combination of the effects of both vegetation and surface.

Given the above, electromagnetic models (EMs) can be used to generate extended synthetic dataset that simulate radar acquisitions in terms of total received signal and its components (e.g., surface, volume, and double-bounce scattering) for different sensor configurations (including signal frequency, polarization, and incidence angle) and soil/vegetation conditions.

In our previous work [4], which is based on the aforementioned premise, a physics-based AI model was designed and trained to estimate the ground related scattering contributions (i.e., surface and double-bounce scattering mechanisms), which are strictly correlated to variations of the soil conditions. In the present study, a new version of the physics-based AI polarimetric decomposition algorithm is

proposed together with a soil moisture retrieval AI model. Explainable AI is a critical aspect of this research. By using AI models and EM simulations, the goal is to enhance the interpretability of the estimation so that they are not only accurate but also understandable and trustworthy [5].

2. METHODOLOGY

As mentioned, the proposed approach for soil moisture estimation is based on a composite algorithm which includes a first module, i.e., an AI model designed for polarimetric decomposition of 4x4 Covariance matrices. Then, a second module is devoted to soil moisture retrieval starting from the outcomes of module 1, i.e., the polarimetric scattering contributions. To leverage the supervised learning capabilities of AI algorithms, a sufficiently large training dataset is needed. Therefore, in this section, the training dataset generation procedure and the methodology involving the two AI models, represented in Figure 1, will be described.

Figure 1. Methodology overview. The training process is described. The first AI model is trained to estimate soil-related contributions starting from Covariance matrices (C4). Then the estimated outcomes are used, as input, to train the second AI model for soil moisture estimation.

2.1 Training dataset simulation

As a first step, the physics of the problem is transferred from electromagnetic modeling to the AI algorithm to include a comprehensive description of SAR scattering process in the retrieval procedure. In this context, the “Tor Vergata” electromagnetic model [6] was adopted to produce a series of simulated C4 matrices.

The EM model also provides the backscatter components that account for the different canonical scattering mechanisms (i.e., double-bounce, volume, and surface scattering) for the four linear polarizations, i.e., VV, VH, HV and HH. The “Tor Vergata” model offers the capability to simulate data by varying vegetation- and soil-related parameters, such as the size and the moisture of the vegetation elements and soil moisture/roughness, while configuring sensor parameters like frequency and incidence angle. Various scenarios involving different corn plant growth stages, soil roughness, and soil moisture levels were considered to generate the simulated data. On the other hand, a single sensor configuration was set to match the SAOCOM-like simulated case studies in terms of signal frequency and incidence angle. By running the EM model, a simulated dataset composed by ~5000 samples is obtained.

2.2 Module 1 – Polarimetric Decomposition

The intrinsic physics information embedded within the training dataset constitutes the foundation for the first Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to establish its mapping criteria during the training process, resulting in the characterization of the AI model as physics aware. Specifically, the polarimetric decomposition model is designed to estimate 6 quantities which consist of the two soil-related scattering contributions, i.e., surface and doublebounce scattering in three polarizations (VV, HH and VH) starting from the C4 matrix associated to the total received signal. To reduce the vegetation effects, the related attenuation is removed from the two simulated scattering contributions so that the AI model can learn how to extract information about the actual conditions of the soil from the total signal. However, being the double-bounce contribution dependent on the plant’s development, removing the vegetation effect associated to the corn stalks is unfeasible. Nonetheless, attenuation by canopies and stalks can be eliminated. Thus, despite the susceptibility to variations in plant structure, the not-attenuated double-bounce component was selected as input for the soil moisture retrieval algorithm, due to its sensitivity to ground dielectric properties.

The ANN consists of a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) architecture composed by an input layer of 16 neurons which correspond to the 4 diagonal elements and the 6 off-diagonal complex entries of the upper half of C4, split into real and imaginary parts, resulting in a total of 16 input features. It is worth mentioning that the choice of considering also the offdiagonal elements is motivated by their correlation information between the different available channels [7] which can be exploited to enhance the estimation of the scattering contributions. Two hidden layers composed by 16 neurons and an output layer of 6 elements complete the network. Concerning the hyperparameters, the model was trained within 30.000 epochs with a learning rate equal to 0.001, an Adam optimizer and the Mean Squared Error as loss

function to be minimized during the training. The dataset was split in train and test set with a 70/30 criterium and normalization was applied to all input variables before training.

2.3 Module 2 – Soil moisture retrieval

The second step is the development of an AI model designated for retrieving soil moisture using as input the estimated ground-related scattering contributions obtained from the AI-based polarimetric decomposition. The soil moisture values used to generate the simulations were selected as target (Figure 1). Two models, i.e., an ANN and a Random Forest (RF) algorithm, were implemented and employed to understand how the performances vary when changing model typology, i.e., Neural Networks and Decision Trees. Considering the first retrieval model, the chosen topology for the network features a basic MLP that includes the 6 input variables, a single hidden layer consisting of 16 nodes, and a single output node corresponding to the soil moisture estimated values, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Architecture of the implemented ANN for soil moisture retrieval. The input of the model are the 2 estimated scattering contributions in the three selected polarizations.

As hyperparameters, the selected number of epochs and a learning rate are equal to 10000 and 0.01, respectively. Moreover, an Adam optimizer and the Mean Squared Error as loss function showed the best results. As for the first model, the train/test split procedure and the normalization of the inputs were applied before training.

The same procedure was adopted before running the other soil moisture retrieval model, i.e., the RF algorithm. The optimal number of estimators, which correspond to the number of trees populating the “forest”, is set to 200.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the previous section, we tried to provide a comprehensive overview of the proposed methodology, aiming to give readers a detailed understanding of the idea behind this work. The results obtained from our previous analyses [4] set the

foundation for the present study, positioned as a natural continuation of the research.

This section intends to present and discuss results related to the entire proposed process of soil moisture estimation. To assess the performances of the proposed approach, the two AI modules were tested on simulated C4 matrices related to the selected case studies.

Particularly, the field campaign was conducted by the Argentinian Space Agency (CONAE) over a small subset of the “Monte Buey” site between October 2019 and February 2020. Five corn fields were selected for the present study. Phenological data, such as plant height, and crucial information about soil conditions, including soil moisture content, were collected. Additionally, L-band SAOCOM acquisitions, acquired over the area within the same time frame, were used to emulate the SAOCOM sensor configuration when generating the C4 matrices. This choice is motivated by the intent to utilize synthetic data for evaluating the performances of the proposed approach within the simulated domain, with the goal of transitioning to real data in the future.

Concerning the first AI model, it is worth analyzing how the scattering contributions are estimated. Notably, in Figure 3 it is possible to observe that the estimated components obtained by running the model on the test set closely match their simulated counterparts. Precisely, the obtained Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is less than 1 dB, regardless of polarization.

Figure 3. Scatterplot representing the comparison between simulated backscatter components and the estimated ones considering the three polarizations.

To have a comprehensive understanding of the physical meaning behind the model outcomes, the simulated SAOCOM-like C4 matrices (related to each corn field and the measurements dates) were ingested by the first AI model. The temporal trend of the two scattering contributions was analyzed to evaluate the correlation with soil moisture variations during the entire growing period. As represented in

Figure 4, the variations in the estimated surface scattering are strictly correlated to the variation of soil moisture occurring during the selected period. On the other hand, double-bounce component appears to be not sensitive to soil moisture during the initial growing stage of corn plants. Then, when the vegetation structure is well developed, small fluctuations associated to the soil moisture variations are observed. These results, which are consistent for all the 5 corn fields, suggest that the ANN can reproduce the physics processes articulated in the EM model employed to populate the training dataset. Moreover, the AI model demonstrates its ability to estimate not attenuated scattering contributions starting from a total C4 matrix which, on the contrary, includes the attenuation effects.

Figure 4. Temporal trend of the estimated scattering contributions to analyze the correlation with soil moisture variations occurring on one corn field. The estimated double-bounce is represented in red while surface scattering is represented in blue. On-site soil moisture measurements are represented as grey bars.

Subsequently, the second model was employed for soil moisture retrieval starting from the estimated soil-related contributions over the simulated case studies (the five Argentinian corn fields). As mentioned, the two soil moisture retrieval models were trained, and their performances compared. Examination of the outcomes, as emphasized in Figure 5, reveals a notable agreement between the estimated soil moisture values and the in-situ measurements. In particular, a RMSE of $\sim 2.8\%$ and 3.0% is achieved by the ANN model and the RF algorithm, respectively, showing that the two algorithms have similar performances.

Figure 5. Scatterplot representing the comparison between the field soil moisture measurements and the estimated values with the ANN model and the RF algorithm.

To conclude, this study aims to demonstrate the potential synergy between physics-aware AI models and PolSAR data for accurate soil moisture retrieval by exploring its applicability within the simulated domain. The AI models leverage the physics contained in the training dataset to produce physically meaningful results. This approach aligns with the concept of scientific explainability, as the physical validity of the obtained results proves that, if properly trained, the AI models are not just black boxes. The significant accuracies achieved are partly due to the absence of noise typical of synthetic data. Future developments will prioritize transitioning from the simulated to the real data domain to investigate the applicability and robustness of the proposed approach through a validation procedure.

4. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank CONAE for providing the SAOCOM images and sharing the in-situ measurements from the field campaign. This work was supported in part by the Italian Space Agency (ASI) through the CLEXIDRA Project and partially funded by the European Union with the AI4AGRI project. The AI4AGRI project entitled “Romanian Excellence Center on Artificial Intelligence on Earth Observation Data for Agriculture” received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101079136. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Hosseini, Mehdi, and Heather McNairn. "Using multi-polarization C-and L-band synthetic aperture radar to estimate biomass and soil moisture of wheat fields." *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 58 (2017): 50-64.
- [2] Sekertekin, Alihsan, Aycan Murat Marangoz, and Saygin Abdikan. "ALOS-2 and Sentinel-1 SAR data sensitivity analysis to surface soil moisture over bare and vegetated agricultural fields." *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 171 (2020): 105303.
- [3] Hajnsek, I., Jagdhuber, T., Schon, H., & Papathanassiou, K. P. (2009). Potential of estimating soil moisture under vegetation cover by means of PolSAR. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 47(2), 442-454
- [4] Papale, L. G., Del Frate, F., Guerriero, L., Schiavon, G., & Bouchat, J. (2023, July). Physics-Based ML and Polarimetric SAR for Soil Moisture Retrieval. In *IGARSS 2023-2023 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium* (pp. 1930-1933). IEEE.
- [5] Datcu, Mihai, et al. "Explainable, physics-aware, trustworthy artificial intelligence: A paradigm shift for synthetic aperture radar." *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine* 11.1 (2023): 8-25.
- [6] M. Bracaglia, P. Ferrazzoli, and L. Guerriero, "A fully polarimetric multiple scattering model for crops," *Remote Sens. Env.*, pp. 170-179, 1995.
- [7] López-Martínez, C., Pottier, E. (2021). Basic Principles of SAR Polarimetry. In: Hajnsek, I., Desnos, YL. (eds) Polarimetric Synthetic Aperture Radar. Remote Sensing and Digital Image Processing, vol 25. Springer, Cham